

THE NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR

Mamayunusov Temurbek Olimovich

Independent researcher of the "Silk Road" International
University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage
Author's email: Mamayunusov97@mail.ru
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Abstract: Currently, the role of innovations in our country is significantly increasing. This is due to the fact that in a market economy, innovation has begun to be recognized as a means of competition, since innovation helps to reduce costs, increase profits, create new needs, increase cash flow, improve the image of the manufacturer of a new product, organize new domestic and foreign markets and directly conquer them. In the article, the author substantiates the necessity and importance of innovative development of the tourism industry based on logical arguments.

Key words: tourism, service, innovation, profit, consumer, tax, innovation, management, intensive, enterprise, efficiency.

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda mamlakatimizda innovatsiyalarning roli sezilarli darajada oshib bormoqda. Buning sababi shundaki, bozor iqtisodiyotida innovatsiya raqobat vositasi sifatida e'tirof etila boshlandi, chunki innovatsiya tannarxni tushirishga, foydani oshirishga, yangi ehtiyojlarni yaratishga, pul oqimining ko'payishiga, yangi mahsulot ishlab chiqaruvchining imidjini oshirishga, yangi ichki va tashqi bozorlarni tashkil etishga va ularni bevosita zabt etishga yordam beradi. Maqolada muallif tomonidan turizm sohasini innovatsion rivojlantirish zaruriyati va ahamiyati mantaqiy dalillar asosida isbotini topgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, xizmat, innovatsiya, foyda, iste'molchi, soliq, innovatsiya, menejment, intensiv, korxonalar, samaradorlik.

Аннотация: В настоящее время роль инноваций в нашей стране значительно возрастает. Это связано с тем, что в рыночной экономике инновации стали признаваться средством конкуренции, поскольку инновации помогают снизить затраты, увеличить прибыль, создать новые потребности, увеличить денежный поток, улучшить имидж производителя новой продукции, организовать новые внутренние и внешние рынки и непосредственно завоевать их. В статье автор на основе логических аргументов обосновывает необходимость и важность инновационного развития туристической отрасли.

Ключевые слова: туризм, услуга, инновации, прибыль, потребитель, налог, инновации, менеджмент, интенсив, предприятие, эффективность.

Introduction. Nowadays, tourism has become an important sector that affects the development of the economy of many countries. The main advantage of tourism is its significant effect on increasing incomes and creating new jobs. For many regions and countries, this is of paramount importance. There are several factors in the development of tourism, the most important of which is innovation. In a market economy, the development of a country's economy cannot be achieved without innovation. In particular, processes related to innovation are of priority importance for the economies of developing countries [1].

To have a good idea of the role of innovation in economic development at the present stage of human development, it is worth noting that 90% of the growth of the gross domestic product of developed countries is formed due to new knowledge and technologies[2]. Innovation is a law of human society, a constant force in the development of society, its product and the main factor of development in general[3]. The term “innovation” as a new economic category was scientifically substantiated by the Austrian and American scientist Y. Schumpeter in the first decade of the 20th century, and a number of “new combinations” he developed indicate the rise of the economy at that time.[4] Under the concept of innovation, he meant the introduction of new types of consumer products, new forms of production, new forms of organization of markets and changes in their use [5].

Analysis and results. Nowadays, the role of innovations in our country is significantly increasing. This is due to the fact that in a market economy, innovation has begun to be recognized as a means of competition, since innovation helps to reduce costs, increase profits, create new needs, increase cash flow, improve the image of the manufacturer of a new product, organize new domestic and foreign markets and directly conquer them. Innovations can manifest themselves as a process or product that significantly affects the increase in the income of an enterprise[6]. Such a process or product (service) is also directly relevant for enterprises in the tourism sector. Since tourism is one of the most important areas of service provision, it requires innovative forms and mechanisms of services provided to customers by this sector.

It should be emphasized that in today's conditions of strong competition, all sectors of the economy, including the tourism sector, cannot develop without innovations. However, many enterprises are not ready to apply innovations in

practice. Because innovations are associated with a high level of risk. Especially if the innovation needs to be applied not to a specific type of service or a specific product of the enterprise, but to the entire activity of the enterprise, in such cases the head of the enterprise does not want to use innovations and face risks.

However, enterprises cannot completely eliminate risk in the process of conducting their activities, but a well-qualified, experienced manager will find an opportunity to reduce the level of risk. Therefore, any enterprise that wants to develop, including tourism enterprises, must accept innovations and implement them in its activities. In our research, we set ourselves the goal of highlighting the use of innovations in the development of tourism enterprises to increase their efficiency.

Realizing the huge potential of tourism in Uzbekistan, sharply increasing its role in improving the national economy, and strengthening its position in creating new jobs requires the transition of this industry from a traditional model of development to an innovative model. Serious measures are being taken in this regard in our country. In particular, an innovative project is being implemented to create a large tourist cluster in the Yellowstone National Park and Grand Canyon of the USA on the basis of the Bakhmal and Zamin districts of the Jizzakh region[7].

In this regard, it is necessary to substantiate the importance and necessity of developing tourism in Uzbekistan on an innovative basis based on logical arguments. Firstly, at the current stage of human society's development, innovations create an opportunity to quickly and sustainably improve the national economy of Uzbekistan based on the application of modern achievements of science and technology, new technologies, new products, new means of communication, new types of services, new methods of management and satisfying the needs of the population. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On Approval of the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Country" of September 21, 2018 stated in this regard: "The rapid introduction of modern innovative technologies into economic sectors, social and other areas, with the widespread use of scientific and technical achievements, is an important condition for the rapid development of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[8].

In this regard, the Head of State approved the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021 and the "Roadmap" for its implementation, as well as the target indicators for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030[9].

The effectiveness of innovative development is determined by the degree to which it covers all types of human activity and all sectors and branches of the national economy. Tourism, as an important component of the national economy, is no exception in this regard. The intensive changes taking place in the tourism sector, on the one hand, the continuous growth of demand for tourism services, on the other hand, make its innovative development an urgent necessity, and also ensure the active participation of this sector in integration processes. The emergence and implementation of innovations in the tourism sector creates the basis for the implementation of systematic, interconnected and highly positive changes in this sector.

Secondly, the tourism sector attracts a large amount of resources and their effective use on an innovative basis is the main condition for the rapid and sustainable development of the sector. In accordance with the proposal adopted at the Rio de Janeiro Conference in 1992, sustainable development is the development achieved without allowing the complete depletion of resources, leaving opportunities for future generations. Thus, the main idea of sustainable development is to achieve the most efficient, that is, extremely economical use of valuable, rare and unique resources. Because some types of economic resources are not renewable, and their careful use becomes an urgent necessity. In our opinion, the idea of sustainable development lies at the heart of the main problem of the economy. Meeting the ever-growing needs of the world's population is fraught with resource shortages. The concept of sustainable development applies equally to all sectors and industries of the economy, including tourism, and requires the efficient use of economic resources in each of them, and the highest economic effect from each resource consumption.

Based on the above, we drew attention to the need to apply the concept of sustainable development to the tourism sector. The rapid growth of demand for tourism services requires a corresponding increase in the resources attracted to the sector. This further increases the urgency of the problem of efficient use of resources attracted to the sector.

Thirdly, under the direct influence of the acceleration of globalization processes, the competitive environment in the tourism market is becoming increasingly acute, and innovative development has become the main factor in increasing the competitiveness of tourism products in the world market. One of the distinctive features of the tourism sector is its high profitability. We believe that it is its high profitability and ability to provide high social impact that increase the interest of all countries in its rapid development and the use of the

positive aspects embodied in the sector. As a result, new tourist facilities are being launched, new tourist products are being created, new enterprises and organizations are being established, qualified personnel are being attracted, and other innovative means of strengthening their position in the competitive struggle are being created. Innovations, their emergence, implementation, and operation are the primary means of strengthening the position of tour operators and travel agents in the tourist services market and increasing their competitiveness.

Fourth, the need to transfer tourism in Uzbekistan to an innovative path of development is explained by the slow pace of development in this sector of the country, low indicators of the use of tourism potential, weak position in the world tourism market, inability to withstand international comparisons and equalizations. We believe that the reasons for this situation in the tourism sector in our country are the following: instability of tax and budget policies, imperfection of the legal and regulatory framework for regulating the tourism sector, the quality of tourist services that does not meet demand, ineffective pricing policy, poorly developed tourist infrastructure, shortage of investment resources, lack of qualified personnel, etc. Fifth, the continuously growing real incomes of the population of the world, the increasing share of services in its consumption structure, as a result of which the demand for tourist services, especially their quality, is dynamically growing, which also requires the development of innovative activities in the sector.

Conclusion. The prospects for growth in demand for tourism services are broad and limitless. Due to the emergence of new types of tourism, the growth of the population and its income, and the increasing demand for quality tourist services, the demand for services in the sector is also growing continuously. These factors, together with the dynamic growth of the gross income of the world's population, ensure the stable and rapid growth of tourism.

Innovations and their widespread use are of high social importance for tourism enterprises and organizations. In a separate tourism enterprise, organizational innovations (for example, scientific organization of labor, innovative management) serve to alleviate physical labor, improve working conditions for employees, and reduce the share of manual labor in total labor costs. The introduction of technological innovations in a tourism enterprise or organization allows increasing the skills of employees, increasing labor productivity, increasing wage income, and increasing the gross income and profit of the enterprise based on saving resources.

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